

Pyroelectric power generator for autonomous systems

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Summary

Developing sustainable electricity sources remains a critical challenge of this century. Pyroelectric materials offer a promising approach for transforming waste heat into electric power. However, their practical application has been constrained by very low power outputs, typically ranging from microwatts to milliwatts. Here we present a macroscopic pyroelectric generator that continuously delivers 1 W of electric power by running an Olsen cycle with 4.3 cm³ of active pyroelectric material. Moreover, the maximum power density of our generator reaches 400 W per litre of active materials. We also demonstrate an autonomous system exclusively powered by a pyroelectric generator following a Stirling cycle. This advancement underscores the potential of nonlinear pyroelectric generators as a highly competitive technology for harvesting low-grade waste energy.

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Introduction

Over 60% of global energy production is lost as waste heat,¹ which can be converted to electricity using thermoelectric and pyroelectric technologies.²⁻⁷ Thermoelectric devices generate power from temperature gradients, while pyroelectric devices exploit temporal temperature changes. Thermoelectric technology is leading in waste heat recovery but requires large temperature gradients between its hot and cold sides.⁸ Despite the improvements, the primary challenge with thermoelectric generators remains sustaining a significant temperature gradient. This difficulty arises from the limited heat exchange surface area and high thermal conductivity of thermoelectric materials,⁶ which demand large prototype volume for substantial heat flows and reduce system power density.^{9, 10} More importantly, a large gradient restricts the ability to harvest low-temperature heat below 100°C, which accounts for 63% of global waste heat.¹

Pyroelectric generators can operate at temperatures below 100°C and rely on relatively small temperature variations.¹¹⁻¹⁶ Non-linear pyroelectric materials, which experience electric-field-driven phase transitions,^{17, 18} offer enhanced energy harvesting compared to linear materials through thermodynamic cycles.¹⁹⁻²¹ Lheritier et al. recently demonstrated that a nonlinear energy harvester with 4.8 cm³ of active lead scandium tantalate multilayer capacitors can capture 11 J in one-shot Olsen cycle within 4 minutes.²² Despite this significant energy gain up to Joule-level, the power output remains low at 50 mW. Indeed, pyroelectric generators suffer from very low power outputs, typically ranging from microwatts to several milliwatts,^{5, 23, 24} making them not competitive with thermoelectric generators. The best pyroelectric power densities have been obtained with thin films deposited on substrates, reaching 526 W cm⁻³.¹⁸ This large value stems from the short time it takes to exchange heat with the large substrate beneath. However, the presence of the substrate prevents a mere scale-up of such films, which in turn forbids the translation of such large power densities into absolute power. Using films is nonetheless one of the keys to reach high power not only thanks to a

larger heat exchange but also to a much better capability to withstand large electric field, contrary to bulk. But the substrate must disappear. The best way to do this is to assemble films in multilayer capacitors, as shown in our previous work²² and also in this study.

To achieve a breakthrough in pyroelectric power generation, two main goals must be met: achieving high power outputs and ensuring sustainability. While current research often focuses on microscopic electric displacement (D) versus electric field (E) loops or one-shot Olsen cycle, these approaches do not prioritize sustainability. The former is common, while the latter has been demonstrated only by Olsen et al.,²⁰ Nguyen et al.²⁵ and Lheritier et al.²². Notably, a continuous macroscopic pyroelectric generator capable of generating power in the watt range, over long period of time, has yet to be developed.

Here we present a sustainable pyroelectric generator utilizing $\text{PbSc}_{0.5}\text{Ta}_{0.5}\text{O}_3$ (PST) multilayer capacitors and the thermodynamic Olsen cycle, capable of generating up to one watt of power. The prototype employs 0.5 mm-thick PST capacitors arranged in a parallel matrix with a double-loop system for alternating hot and cold dielectric fluids (**Figure 1**). A key feature of this system is the usage of hot and cold reservoirs, authorizing the accumulation of hot and cold liquids in separate places. This renders pyroelectric generators much better suited to converting waste heat in electricity. Besides, this system modulates the electric field to induce strong nonlinear pyroelectric effect by adjusting temperature variation over time. Finite element modelling indicates that optimizing the Olsen cycle and increasing flow rate are keys for improving power output. Note that this approach combining active materials and a fluid transporting heat has been recently identified by Qian and Takeuchi as the only way to scale-up caloric devices – a sister topic to pyroelectric energy harvesters – after having analysed tens of devices²⁶.

Three generator variants were tested: GEN1 (60 capacitors), GEN2 (154 capacitors), and GEN3 (255 capacitors), operating at an Olsen cycling frequency of 0.2 Hz. GEN1 and GEN2 produced 0.4 W and 0.9 W, respectively, at 500 V, with respective active power densities of 400 W L^{-1} and 350 W L^{-1} . GEN3 generated 1 W at 350 V with an

active power density of 233 W L^{-1} . Our generators outperform previous nonlinear pyroelectric generators by a factor of 20, and linear pyroelectric generators by three orders of magnitude. Moreover, the maximum device power density per unit temperature variation reaches $0.85 \text{ W L}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$, thanks to its smaller temperature span, compact size, and fluid-based heat transfer. Our study demonstrates the considerable potential of pyroelectric power generators in converting waste heat into electricity when thermodynamic cycles are used.

Results

Pyroelectric power generation prototype

The power is calculated as $N/t = N \times f$, where N denotes the harvested energy that is proportional to temperature variation ΔT , t is the cycle period, and f is the frequency. To enhance power output, it is essential to achieve both, a short cycle period and a large ΔT . Improving heat exchange is therefore crucial.²⁷

We developed an enhanced the power generation prototype starting from Lheritier's design²². **Figure 1a** depicts the prototype designed for nonlinear pyroelectric power generation. The setup includes two reservoirs of silicone oil: one heated by a hot plate as the hot source and another cooled down with ice as the cold source. A peristaltic pump cyclically circulates the silicone oil through the multilayer capacitors and pours it out in a storage reservoir. Solenoid valves, controlled by Python code and a solenoid driver, switch between hot and cold cycles to create temperature variations over time (**Figure 1b**). Another sourcemeter, Keithley 2410, also controlled by Python, manages capacitor charge and discharge. Further details are in the **Methods** section and Supplementary **Note 1**.

Our prototype offers three major improvements over previous design²². Firstly, we significantly shortened the fluid circuits to reduce thermal losses. Secondly, we implemented a dual-loop configuration to further minimize thermal losses by separating the hot and cold fluid circuits. Thirdly, instead of implementing eight generators

connected in parallel²², we concentrated all capacitors into a single unit. This integration maximized fluid velocity and improved heat exchange efficiency. Further details are in Supplementary **Note 2 and 3**.

To enhance heat exchange between the fluid and the regenerator, the latter consists of 0.5 mm-thick PST multilayer capacitors stacked with spacers (double-sided tape) on both sides, which are electrically connected in parallel using silver epoxy (Supplementary **Figure S2**). Width of the slits is 8 mm, and their thickness is 0.42 mm. Such a configuration has been previously used in electrocaloric coolers^{28, 29} and pyroelectric generators²². The entire generator was assembled with a soft heat-shrinking tube (Supplementary **Figure S1**), chosen for its good thermal insulation properties. Additional details on such multilayer capacitors can be found in Supplementary **Note 1**, as well as in our previous works^{28, 29}.

As mentioned earlier, we employed the Olsen cycle to achieve power generation, as described by Olsen in his pioneering work on pyroelectric energy harvesting during the 1980s.²⁰ **Figure 1b** illustrates how to implement Olsen cycling using our prototype. A standard Olsen cycle (typically denoted as ABCD, **Figure 1b**) includes two isothermal and two isofield states: A→B: Charge capacitors at the coldest temperature (isothermal); B→C: Maintain a constant electric field and heat up the capacitors (isofield); C→D: Discharge capacitors at the hottest temperature (isothermal); D→A: Cool down the capacitors at zero field (isofield). The entire Olsen cycle can be represented as A→B→C→D→A. During states DA and AB, the cold fluid circuit is active, while during states BC and CD, the hot fluid circuit is active.

Finite element modelling of heat exchange

We used COMSOL 5.5 to model heat exchange between fluids and pyroelectric elements, with details in Supplementary **Note 2**. The simulation began with a fluid inflow at 110°C and a flow rate of 600 mL min⁻¹ through the generator, starting from 10°C, simulating the heating phase of an Olsen cycle. The time-dependent average generator temperature $T_{gen}(t)$ (**Figure 2a**) shows two distinct phases with different heat

exchange rates. For the GEN1 configuration (60 capacitors in a 10×6 array), reaching 80% of the temperature change from 10°C to 90°C took 1.3 seconds (Part I in **Figure 2a**). However, as the temperature approached 110°C, heat transfer significantly slowed down, with an additional 2.3 seconds required to reach the maximum T_{gen} (Part II in **Figure 2a**). In practice, Part II takes even longer due to thermal losses, as shown experimentally in **Figure 2d**. This slowdown occurs because the heat exchange rate decreases as the temperature difference between the fluid and the capacitors narrows down, a phenomenon that also affects the cooling phase of the Olsen cycle.

Part II's temperature range significantly exceeds the phase transition temperature of PST (25°C)³⁰. Since efficient energy harvesting usually happens near the phase transition, energy harvested in Part II is minimal. Therefore, discharging (or charging) capacitors near the end of Part I, instead of at isothermal states, maximizes energy capture and significantly shortens the cycle period, as will be confirmed experimentally.

We applied this strategy to a full Olsen cycle, simulating both cooling and heating phases with GEN2 parameters (Supplementary **Note 2**). The inflow temperature T_{in} was modelled as a periodic rectangular function with a 5-second cycle: 2.5 seconds for cooling at 0°C and 2.5 seconds for heating at 127°C, starting from an initial temperature T_{gen} of 25°C. We analysed $T_{gen}(t)$ profiles with flow rates from 100 to 600 mL min⁻¹ (Supplementary **Figure S5**). As flow rate increased, ΔT_{gen} also increased, reaching 100°C after 2.5 seconds at 600 mL min⁻¹ (Supplementary **Figure S8**). Higher flow rates enhance heat exchange by reducing the thermal boundary layer resistance and, at very high velocities, by inducing turbulence that disrupts this layer (Supplementary **Figure S6**).

Compare ΔT between modelling and experiments

We simulated inflow temperature T_{in} , outflow temperature T_{out} , and T_{gen} profiles over 20 cycles using GEN2 configuration at 600 mL min⁻¹ (Supplementary **Figure S7a and b**). T_{out} profile closely follows $T_{gen}(t)$ with a phase shift, indicating that the unmeasurable T_{gen} can be inferred from the measurable T_{out} . Consequently, we

experimentally measured T_{in} and T_{out} by inserting thermocouples at the inlet and outlet ends (Supplementary **Figure S1**). The results match well our model's predictions (Supplementary **Figure S7**).

Modifying Olsen cycle

Following our model's predictions, we modified the classical Olsen cycle by discharging the capacitors earlier, instead of waiting until the generator reaches an isothermal state. To validate this, we conducted one-shot tests of both the classical and modified Olsen cycles using GEN1 with 60 capacitors at 200 V. Based upon the model, we also applied a high flow rate of 600 mL min^{-1} . A Keithley 2410 sourcemeter was employed for charging and discharging GEN1 while simultaneously monitoring the applied voltage $U(t)$ and current $I(t)$. The energy was determined by integrating the product of voltage and current with respect to time. In this context, positive energy values indicate charged energy, while negative values denote harvested energy (defined as N).

Figure 2b presents the $U(t)$ and $I(t)$ for the classical Olsen cycle. A significant peak (highlighted by the dashed box in **Figure 2b**) was observed in $I(t)$ at the onset of the BC leg, attributed to the pyroelectric effect as T_{gen} rapidly increases. The pyroelectric current (I_p) can be expressed as $Ap(dT/dt)$, where A is the cross-section area of the effective electrodes and p is the pyroelectric coefficient expressed as (dD/dT) . The sharp I_p peak arises from the first segment of the heat exchange curves closer to the transition temperature, significantly contributing to energy harvesting during the BC leg. This is reflected in the corresponding energy profile over time. This phase lasts around 2 seconds, in line with our model's predictions. However, it requires 7 seconds more to reach the isothermal state for discharging where total N reaches its maximum (1 J). **Figure 2c** shows the $U(t)$ and $I(t)$ of the modified Olsen cycle, with discharges occurring at the peak endpoints of I_p . This modification significantly shortened the BC leg duration by a factor of three, albeit with a roughly 10% loss (0.1 J) in N obtained from BC leg (**Figure 2d**). The total N is 0.95 J, with only a 5% loss.

Continuous power generation

We tested the modified Olsen cycle in a larger version of the generator (GEN3, consisting of 15 rows \times 17 columns = 255 capacitors). The test was conducted with a T_c of 0°C and a T_h of 80°C (Supplementary **Figure S9**), with a cycle period of 5 seconds. **Figure 3** shows the $U(t)$ and $I(t)$ profiles over 10 cycles, as well as the calculated energy profile, tested at a voltage of 350 V. GEN3 harvested 50.0 J over 50 seconds (10 cycles), resulting in a power output of 1.0 W and an active power density of 233 W L⁻¹. Note that the active power density is calculated based on the volume of the capacitors' active materials (16.9 mm³ per PST capacitor).

To increase power density, we tested the modified Olsen cycle at voltage up to 500 V in GEN1, with a reduced cycle period of 4.5 seconds. Tests were performed with T_c at 10°C and T_h at 115°C. Supplementary **Figure S10** shows $U(t)$ and $I(t)$ profiles, as well as the calculated energy profile. For each voltage, power generation tests were carried out over 10 to 20 cycles. At 500 V, 36 J were harvested over 90 seconds (20 cycles), yielding 0.4 W of power, with each cycle harvesting approximately 1.8 J in 4.5 seconds. The active material volume of each capacitor is 16.9 mm³, resulting in a total active volume of 1.0 cm³ for GEN1. The calculated active power density reaches 400 W L⁻¹. The active material constitutes 55% of the total capacitor volume. Accordingly, the overall power density, calculated from the total device volume including the dead layers, is 180 W L⁻¹.

A medium-sized generator (GEN2, 154 capacitors, 11 \times 14 array) was also tested at 500 V harvested 90 J in 100 seconds (20 cycles), producing 0.9 W. Its active power density is 350 W L⁻¹. See Supplementary **Note 4** for details.

Our high energy and power outputs stem from large temperature variations of up to 100°C achieved in a short cycle of 4.5 to 5 seconds. Indeed, as exposed earlier, power is calculated as $N \times f$, which indicates that high power requires both large harvested energy N (ΔT dependent) and high frequency f . However, efficient power generation generally occurs near the phase transition temperature with smaller temperature

variations, as demonstrated by Lheritier²² and Pandya¹⁸. The efficiency of our PST capacitors could reach 40% of Carnot when cycling at 25 – 35°C, as has confirmed in our previous work.²² Thus, efficiency and power are essentially competing parameters, as noted by Olsen in 1982.³¹ In this study, our main objective is to exclusively access power generation, which necessitates a large ΔT and high operation frequency, leading to a relatively low efficiency (1.42% of Carnot, see Supplementary **Note 5**).

Discussions

Comparing power density and power

One key performance metric is active power density, which quantifies the pyroelectric material's ability to generate power. We compared the active power density achieved in this study with those of previously reported nonlinear pyroelectric bulk materials^{20, 22-24, 32-43}, including bulk Pb(Zr,Ti)O₃-based ceramics, P(VDF-TrFE) copolymers, and BaTiO₃-based ceramics (**Figure 4a**). In Olsen's pioneering work in the 1980s, a pyroelectric generator was developed using Pb_{0.99}Nb_{0.02}(Zr_{0.68}Sn_{0.25}Ti_{0.07})_{0.98}O₃ ceramic stacks. He reported a power output of 1.6 W, and an active power density of 33 W L⁻¹ based on the energy value obtained in the first cycle. However, this performance could not be replicated in later cycles due to the degradation of the ceramic stacks. Our best result (400 W L⁻¹) is five times higher than the closest values reported for these materials (78 W L⁻¹ obtained using Pb(Zr,Ti)O₃-Pb(Ni,Nb)O₃ reported in ref. ³⁴). Using the same capacitors, our generator achieves a 50-fold increase in power density compared to our previous work²², due to improvements in heat exchange, the Olsen cycle, and flow rates. Additionally, our best power output (1 W, obtained with an Olsen cycle) is 20 times higher than the closest values reported for nonlinear pyroelectric generators (50 mW in ref. ²²) and three orders of magnitude higher than those of linear generators, as shown in **Figure 4b**. Note that the power or active power density values reported for previous nonlinear pyroelectric generators were not obtained through

continuous measurements but only microscopic *D-E* loops or one-shot experiments, as mentioned in the introduction section.

Another critical performance metric is the device's compactness,⁴⁴ referred as device power density. Our prototype exhibits a device power density per unit temperature variation of $0.85 \text{ W L}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$. Note that the volume used for device power densities calculations includes the entire physical volume of the generator from inlet to outlet. This enhancement is attributed to the compact size, fluid-based heat transfer and smaller temperature variation requirements of our prototype. Furthermore, should our prototype have the capability to utilize water as a heat transfer medium, pending resolution of waterproofing challenges, it would offer notable advantages, due to water's higher density and thermal capacity. This is what modelling tells us, as detailed in the following section.

Self-maintained system with Stirling cycles

The Olsen cycle is the one that produces the largest amount of energy. However, it necessitates a power supply or complex electronics to maintain constant voltage when the temperature is rising. An alternative is Stirling cycle, in which Olsen's constant voltage step is replaced with a constant charge step. This makes this cycle much easier to run and closer to sustainability because there is no need for power supply. We prepared a new regenerator GEN4 with a similar configuration as our previous Olsen's cycle (15 rows x 17 columns = 255 capacitors). The Stirling cycle was operated between $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with a total cycle period of 5.4 seconds. An initial charging voltage of only 38 V was applied. A maximum voltage amplification up to 350 V was induced by the temperature rise. GEN4 harvested 21 J over 38 seconds (7 cycles), corresponding to a power output of 0.55 W, which represents 55% of the power harvested using the Olsen cycle (see details in Supplementary Note 7).

To exemplify the sustainability of our approach, we prepared a self-maintained system able to communicate regularly with a mobile phone, sending temperature and positioning (pitch and roll angles) information (see Supplementary Note 8). This system

(GEN6) is based on a Stirling cycle that does not require any power supply, contrary to Olsen cycles. It contains 60 capacitors cycled between 10°C and 60°C. It contains a microcontroller controlling the valves and an RF module programmed to communicate with a mobile with a dedicated app (see Supplementary Note 8). We tested the system for 30 minutes, transforming enough heat into electricity to make the system self-maintained, continuously sending information to a mobile phone.

As our strategy is to accumulate hot and cold fluids in two different reservoirs, we need a pump. We used our model to estimate the fluidic power required to move the fluid in our device (see Supplementary Note 9). With a pressure of 4.5 kPa and a flow rate of 600 mL min⁻¹, the power required to move the fluid is only 45 mW, which is 20 times less than the generated energy.

Outlook

The performance of our generator can be significantly improved with several strategies. First, modelling suggests that using water as the working fluid and reducing capacitors' and slits' thicknesses by half could twofold increase the cycling frequency. Second, upgrading to a more powerful pump to boost flow rates, and at sufficient flow rate, inducing turbulence for better heat exchange. Third, using a power supply with higher current capacity, along with heat transfer improvements, could shorten the cycle period. As predicted by the model (Supplementary Note 6), using water, 0.25 mm-thick capacitors and slits, and disregarding charge/discharge time, at a flow rate of 1 L min⁻¹ GEN1's cycle period could be reduced to 1.2 seconds, potentially increasing the active power density to 1500 W L⁻¹. Last but not least, it is anticipated that even higher B-site ordering would further improve the material's pyroelectric properties. Furthermore, the pursuit of sustainable applications necessitates the development of lead-free alternatives. These strategies promise immediate performance improvements and considerable potential for pyroelectric prototypes in waste heat recovery.

Methods

PST multilayer capacitors fabrications: PST multilayer capacitors were prepared using solid-state reaction and tape casting methods, with detailed preparation and characterization processes reported in Ref. ^{22, 28, 29}. The PST multilayer capacitor exhibits B-site ordering of around 0.75, achieved by sintering at 1400°C followed by a 1000-hour annealing at 1000°C. The 0.5 mm-thick capacitor consist of 11 layers of 38.6 μm-thick PST and 10 layers of 2.05 μm-thick Pt electrodes, with 9 inner PST layers intercalated between Pt electrodes. Terminal electrodes were fabricated with silver paste. This design results in 54.5% of PST being active, corresponding to the portion between Pt inner electrodes, with an active electrode area of 48.7 mm². Each PST capacitor measures 10.4 mm (L) × 7.2 mm (W) × 0.5 mm (T). The details of PST capacitor are shown in Supplementary Table S1 and S2.

Experimental setup: The experimental setups are depicted in Figure S1. Silicone oil (viscosity 5 cSt at 25°C, Sigma Aldrich), as detailed in Table S1, was utilized to transfer heat from the sources to the generator. The hot reservoir was regulated using a heated hot plate and magnetic stirring, while the cold reservoir was maintained at zero or sub-zero temperatures using ice or ice-salts mixture. A peristaltic pump, powered by an external power supply, circulated the fluid through the generators and into a storage reservoir. Control of the Keithley 2400 was accomplished using a laptop with Python code, which regulated pinch valves (Bio-Chem, DC12V) or solenoid valves (Burkert, DC24V) to switch between hot and cold fluid circuits, as illustrated in Figure S1a and S1b, according to the stages of the Olsen cycles. Temperature measurements were taken with two thermocouples (RS PRO Type K Exposed Junction) positioned at the inlet and outlet. Python code was also employed to control the Keithley 2410, managing the charging and discharging of capacitors while recording voltage and current values. Specifically, the voltage source mode with a current compliance of 20 mA was used for these capacitor operations. Additionally, the laptop also recorded the temperature data from the thermocouples.

Generator configurations: The generator structure comprises 0.5 mm-thick PST capacitors stacked with double-sided tape spacers and electrically connected in parallel using silver epoxy (CircuitWorks) with copper wires (Figure S2). The slit thickness and width is approximately 0.42 mm and 8 mm, respectively. The entire generator was assembled using a hard wood tube wrapped with a heat-soft shrink tube (Figure S1), chosen for their good thermal insulation properties. Three generators are demonstrated: GEN1 (10 rows \times 6 columns = 60 capacitors), GEN2 (11 rows \times 14 columns = 154 capacitors) and GEN3 (15 rows \times 17 columns = 255 capacitors).

Calculation of energy harvested, power output, active and device power density: We read the voltage and current of the generator using a Keithley 2410 sourcemeter. The energy was calculated by integrating the voltage-current over time, and the power was determined by dividing the harvested energy by the time. Positive values represent the charged energy, while negative values represent the harvested energy. The active power density was determined using the active volume of the PST multilayer capacitors, whereas the device power density was calculated based on the total device volume, measured from the inlet to the outlet.

Resource Availability

Lead contact

Requests for further information and resources should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the lead contact, Emmanuel Defay (emmanuel.defay@list.lu).

Materials availability

This study did not generate new unique reagents.

Data and code availability

This study did not generate any datasets or code.

Raw data

Raw data can be found here <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18221148>

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Author contributions

E.D. suggested the experimental study. T.U. and S.H. prepared the PST-capacitors samples. L.S. and J.L. designed the prototype and ran the GEN2 and GEN3 that led to Figure 2-3, Figure S4.2 – S4.5. L.S. and V.K. ran the GEN1 tests that led to Figure S4.1. L.S., J. L. and A.A. ran the one-shot GEN1 tests that led to Figure 2. V.K. and L.S. wrote the code. U.P. and O.B. assisted to build the prototype. L.S. and V.K. developed the finite element modelling that led to supplementary Note 2, Note 3 and Note 6 and Note 9. YN, AA, MK, FN and VK contributed to build GEN4. AA, NB, OR, JPM, MG contributed to build GEN5. YN wrote Note 7, AA wrote Note 8, LS wrote Note 9. E.D., S.G. and V.K. made valuable contributions to the productive discussions and provided insightful comments. L.S. wrote the manuscript with E.D. and S.G. All authors contributed to the final version of the manuscript. E.D. obtained the funding and supervised the project.

Declaration of Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Main figure titles and legends

Figure 1: Non-linear pyroelectric power generation prototype. **a.** Schematic diagram of the prototype. A computer using Python code manages a power supply to control two valves, circulating dielectric fluid between cold and hot reservoirs. It also operates a second power supply for the generator's charge and discharge, simultaneously collecting voltage, current, and temperature data via thermocouples. A peristaltic pump, powered by a third power supply, runs continuously during the test. **b.** Four steps of an executed Olsen cycle. AB: charge of the generator at a low temperature, BC: maintain a constant voltage, open the hot fluid circuit and close the cold fluid circuit, allowing hot oil to heat up the generator, CD: discharge of the generator at a high temperature, DA: open the cold fluid circuit and close the hot fluid circuit, allowing cold oil to cool down the generator.

Figure 2: Heat exchange modelling for GEN1 configuration (60 capacitors). **a.** Time-dependent average temperature profile of capacitors (T_{gen}) with 110°C silicone oil flow through PST capacitors, starting at 10°C and at a flow rate of 600 mL min⁻¹. **One-shot experiments based on classical and modified Olsen cycles.** **b.** Voltage (black) and current (red) vs. time for the classical Olsen cycle. **c.** Voltage (black) and current (red) vs. time for the modified Olsen cycle. **d.** Energy profiles for classical and modified Olsen cycles, obtained by integrating the voltage-current product over time. Tests were performed with T_c at 10°C, T_h at 95°C, and a flow rate of 600 mL min⁻¹, using a 200 V voltage source with 10 mA current compliance to charge and discharge capacitors. Note that ABCD denotes the standard Olsen cycle, whereas A'B'C'D' refers to the modified Olsen cycle.

Figure 3: Pyroelectric power generation experiment. Voltage (black) and current (red) versus time, as well as the corresponding energy profile (blue) of GEN3 over 10 cycles tested at 350 V. Test was conducted with a T_c at 0°C and a T_h at 80°C . In both experiments, a voltage source mode with a current compliance of 20 mA was used to charge and discharge capacitors. The flow rate is 600 mL min^{-1} .

Figure 4: State-of-the-art pyroelectric power generating. a. Comparison of active

power density in $W L^{-1}$ of active materials with previously reported nonlinear

pyroelectric materials. PZT-based ceramics include PZST²⁰:

$Pb_{0.99}Nb_{0.02}(Zr_{0.68}Sn_{0.25}Ti_{0.07})_{0.98}O_3$; PZNT³²: $Pb(Zn_{1/3}Nb_{2/3})_{0.955}Ti_{0.045}O_3$; PLZT³³:

$(Pb_{0.92}La_{0.08})(Zr_{0.65}Ti_{0.35})O_3$; PNNZT³⁴: $Pb(Zr, Ti)O_3-Pb(Ni, Nb)O_3$. P(VDF-TrFE)

stands for 60/40 P(VDF-TrFE) copolymer reported in ^{35,36}. BTO based ceramic

represents $Ba(Zr_{0.1}Ti_{0.9})O_3$ reported in ³⁷. PST multilayer capacitors stands for

$PbSc_{0.5}Ta_{0.5}O_3$ multilayer capacitors reported in ²², and also used in this work.

Notably, these previous studies assessed power density using either microscopic D-E

loops or one-shot Olsen cycle tests, neither of which are sustainable approaches. b.

Comparison of power in mW with previously reported pyroelectric generators since

2010, including both linear and nonlinear generators.^{22-24,34,36-43}